

Secular Prayers

As referenced in “An Ultimate from Immanence:
Lotus Buddhism Redefined for a Secular Worldview”

The first three of the secular prayers presented here are adaptations of the traditional rituals of Nichiren Shoshu, the Soka Gakkai (SGI), and Nichiren Shu. While the content of each prayer set has been secularized, the ceremonial structures remain the same. This accommodates those transitioning into a secular practice who still prefer their previous format. In the Shoshu and Soka Gakkai rituals, the secular prayers are read in silence, allowing traditional and secular practitioners to practice alongside one another without disturbance.

A key feature of the Shoshu and Shu secular prayers is that they implicitly relegate to the past long-standing sectarian differences over supernatural criteria. For instance, if one accepts the scholarly position that the *Lotus Sūtra*'s revelation of the eternal Buddha is a skillful device, the dispute between Nichiren Shu (Gautama is the eternal Buddha) and Nichiren Shoshu (Nichiren Daishonin is the eternal Buddha) becomes a historical footnote, rooted in the methods of expedient means. As for the Soka Gakkai, which immortalizes its founding presidents as eternal mentors and encourages belief in an all-pervasive life force, secular practitioners now have the option of embracing a teaching cleared of both mentor glorification and vital-essence metaphysics.

The last prayer is for independent practitioners—those who have moved on from traditional groups, were excluded from them, or never had a formal relationship with Lotus Buddhism. These prayers introduce an alternative object of veneration and the option of chanting *Nam Rihō no Chihi Sō* instead of the traditional *Nam/Namu Myōhō Renge Kyō*. By reciting the new invocation, practitioners shift from revering a ‘Mystic Law’ revealed in the *Lotus Sūtra* to revering the wisdom and compassion of the natural order directly.

Nichiren asserted that chanting *Nam Myōhō Renge Kyō* represented the principle of ‘many in body; one in mind.’ The schools of Buddhism following his lead today recite these words; yet, their underlying teachings are a source of conflict between them. Perhaps, in a mystical context, conflicting interpretations don’t matter; merely accepting faith in *Myōhō Renge* is the “one in mind.” In contrast, the following Secular Prayers offer unity through a shared understanding of the teaching itself. In this framework, the ultimate is not a supernatural entity, but becomes a relational dynamic expressed in the phrase: “The conditional emergence of benevolence as gifted by time, process, and potential.” Regardless of sectarian association (‘many in body’), secular practitioners are of ‘one mind’ when they embrace a universal ethic inspired by immanence.

JRT (July 1, 2026)

Secular Shoshu Silent Prayers

The Nichiren Shoshu ritual includes recitations in classical Japanese of the Lotus Sūtra's second chapter (prose section) and the entire sixteenth chapter. The ceremony is performed at home or in a temple before a properly enshrined image of reverence called a Gohonzon. Practitioners typically sit in a pew, on a chair, or in the seiza position. At a minimum, home altar accessories should include a bell, a candle, a cup of water, and fresh greens. During prayer, beads are held in unfolded hands, reverently poised with palms together.

Morning sessions consist of five liturgical recitations lasting about forty-five minutes, while evening sessions include three recitations taking approximately thirty minutes. The Silent Prayers are read during quiet periods after the liturgical sets. Both morning and evening sessions conclude with chanting Nam Myoho Renge Kyō for five minutes or longer.¹

The First Prayer is performed only during the morning prayer session. Face the Gohonzon and, while bowing in reverence, chant *Nam Myoho Renge Kyō* three times. Turn and face east, chant three times again, bow and recite the liturgy from the second chapter and the verse section of the sixteenth chapter of the *Lotus Sūtra*. At the end, chant three times again but this time using the formal version of *Namu Myoho Renge Kyō*. Then, bow, chant *Nam Myoho Renge Kyō* three times, and read the following:

With faith's highest virtue sourced in immanence, the ability to shape our lives in its likeness depends on sincere and thoughtful effort alone. This ceremony supports the effort.

Chant *Nam Myoho Renge Kyō* three times.

The Second Prayer is performed in both the morning and evening prayer sessions. Face the Gohonzon, ring the bell seven times, recite the liturgy from the second chapter of the *Lotus Sūtra*, then ring the bell three times. This is followed by the recitation of both the prose and verse section of the sixteenth chapter. The Second Prayer is the only one in which the entire sixteenth chapter is recited. In closing, chant the formal *Namu Myoho Renge Kyō* three times, ring the bell five times, chant *Nam Myoho Renge Kyō* three times, bow and read the following:

Our sacred image has come to represent the conditional emergence of benevolence as gifted by time, process, and potential. Though relieved of its supernatural foundations, it continues to project an inherent pureness

¹ Based on a review of *The Liturgy of Nichiren Shoshu*, published in 2015 by the Nichiren Shoshu Head Temple, Fujinomiya, Japan. See pp. 32-37. The following two links are to a copy of the traditional Nichiren Shoshu liturgy and a picture of their image of reverence:

<https://web.archive.org/web/20230405044617/http://www.bahaistudies.net/asma/nichireنشoshu.pdf> and

<https://web.archive.org/web/20240215003929/https://i.ebayimg.com/images/g/8v8AAOSwWydlq2Qo/s-l500.jpg>.

that can surpass and better both civil and religious authority, and encourage the pursuit of a more peaceful world.

Chant *Nam Myoho Renge Kyō* three times while facing the Gohonzon.

The Third Prayer is performed in both the morning and evening prayer sessions. Face the Gohonzon, ring the bell seven times, recite the liturgy from the second chapter of the *Lotus Sūtra*, then ring the bell three times. This is followed by recitation of the verse section of the sixteenth chapter. In closing, chant the formal *Namu Myoho Renge Kyō* three times, ring the bell five times, chant *Nam Myoho Renge Kyō* three times, bow and read the following: (There are four parts to this prayer.)

3a: The prayers hereby replaced paid homage to protective deities, an object of worship with extraordinary attributes, Nichiren Daishonin as the eternally compassionate Buddha, and the preservation of his spirit by a lineage of high priests. They also endowed the object of worship, the Daishonin, and the high priests with a beneficial power.

Face the Gohonzon, chant *Nam Myoho Renge Kyō* three times and read the following Silent Prayer.

3b: For some, the transcendent elements of the prior prayers still resonate. For others, they are remnants of the past, especially now when there is a path forward without them.

Face the Gohonzon, chant *Nam Myoho Renge Kyō* three times and read the following Silent Prayer.

3c: To introduce a grounded principle for divine inspiration, the Lotus Sutra's revelation of an ever-present Buddha was interpreted to be a universal ethic established by the temporal realm.

Face the Gohonzon, silently chant *Nam Myoho Renge Kyō* three times and read the following Silent Prayer.

3d: The implications are liberating, for the ultimate insight is no longer limited to a mystical union subject to sectarian custody, but observed firsthand in the natural order and open for emulation based on one's best judgment.

Chant *Nam Myoho Renge Kyō* three times while facing the Gohonzon.

The Fourth Prayer is performed only in the morning session. Face the Gohonzon, ring the bell seven times, recite the liturgy from the second chapter of the *Lotus Sūtra*, then ring the bell three times. This is followed by recitation of the verse section of the sixteenth

chapter. In closing, chant the formal *Namu Myoho Renge Kyō* three times, ring the bell five times, chant *Nam Myoho Renge Kyō* three times, bow and offer the following: (There are two parts to this prayer.)

4a: This practice merges the meaning of these prayers with the rhythm of a twice-daily recitation from chapters two and sixteen of the *Lotus Sūtra*.

Face the Gohonzon and chant *Nam Myoho Renge Kyō* three times.

4b: And, while chanting *Nam Myoho Renge Kyō*, it welcomes reflection on such matters as overcoming difficulties, personal growth, and the advancement of a common good.

Face the Gohonzon and chant *Nam Myoho Renge Kyō* three times.

The Fifth Prayer is performed in both the morning and evening sessions. Face the Gohonzon, ring the bell seven times, recite the liturgy from the second Chapter of the *Lotus Sūtra*, then ring the bell three times. This is followed by recitation of the verse section of the sixteenth Chapter. At the end of this recitation ring the bell seven times while beginning to chant for a minimum of five minutes. To end chanting, chant *Nam Myoho Renge Kyō* three times with a ring of the bell at each syllable of the last *Myoho Renge Kyō*. Then, the following:

5a: Before closing, a few moments of appreciation for those held dear.

Ring the bell continuously while paying respects. Then, face the Gohonzon, chant *Nam Myoho Renge Kyō* three times, and read:

5b: We pray to carry on with a tradition long dedicated to cultivating a blend of wisdom and compassion in all.

To conclude the prayer session, chant *Nam Myoho Renge Kyō* three times with a ring of the bell at each syllable of the last *Myoho Renge Kyō* while bowing in reverence.

Secular Soka Silent Prayers

*The Soka Gakkai International ritual is a shortened version of the Nichiren Shoshu format, consisting of three prayers in both the morning and evening sessions. The liturgy includes the initial prose section of the Lotus Sūtra's second chapter and the verse section of the sixteenth chapter. As with the Shoshu format, the SGI Silent Prayers are read during quiet periods following the liturgical sets, and the session concludes with chanting Nam Myoho Renge Kyō for five minutes or longer.*²

Preamble (morning only): Prior to beginning the ceremony, sit in the prayers position, bow in reverence, and silently read the following:

With faith's highest virtue sourced in immanence, the ability to shape our lives in its likeness depends on sincere and thoughtful effort alone. This ceremony supports the effort.

First Prayer (morning and evening): To begin the recitation of the liturgy, face the Gohonzon, ring the bell, and chant *Nam Myoho Renge Kyō* three times. Then, after the liturgy is recited, read the following first silent prayer.

Our sacred image has come to represent the conditional emergence of benevolence as gifted by time, process, and potential. Though relieved of its supernatural foundations, it continues to project an inherent pureness that can surpass and better both civil and religious authority, and encourage the pursuit of a more peaceful world.

Chant *Nam Myoho Renge Kyō* three times.

Second Silent Prayer (Part A in the morning and part B in the evening): Face the Gohonzon, ring the bell, chant *Nam Myoho Renge Kyō* three times, and read the designated Silent Prayer.

A: To introduce a grounded principle for divine inspiration, the Lotus Sutra's revelation of an ever-present Buddha was interpreted to be a universal ethic established by the temporal realm. The implications are liberating, for the ultimate insight is no longer limited to a mystical union subject to sectarian custody, but observed firsthand in the natural order and open for emulation based on one's best judgment.

² Based on a review of *The Liturgy of the Soka Gakkai International*, published in 2018 by The World Tribune Press, Santa Monica, CA. See pp. 18-19. The following two links are to a copy of the SGI Silent Prayers and a picture of their image of reverence:

<https://web.archive.org/web/20230924180821/https://chantforhappiness.blogspot.com/2015/12/revised-silent-prayers-for-sgi-members.html>.

https://web.archive.org/web/20211028184523/https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:SGI_Gohonzon.jpg.

B: This practice merges the meaning of these prayers with the rhythm of a twice-daily recitation from chapters two and sixteen of the *Lotus Sūtra*. And, while chanting *Nam Myoho Renge Kyō*, it welcomes reflection on such matters as overcoming difficulties, personal growth, and the advancement of a common good.

Chant *Nam Myoho Renge Kyō* three times.

Third Silent Prayer (morning and evening): Face the Gohonzon, ring the bell, and chant *Nam Myoho Renge Kyō* three times. When finished with the liturgy, ring the bell five times as you begin chanting. Then continue chanting as long as you wish. Afterwards, ring the bell three times and read the following silent prayers:

Before closing, a few moments of appreciation for those held dear.

Ring the bell continuously while bowing and paying respects. Then, face the Gohonzon, chant *Nam Myoho Renge Kyō* three times, and read:

We pray to carry on with a tradition long dedicated to cultivating a blend of wisdom and compassion in all.

To conclude, ring the bell and chant *Nam Myoho Renge Kyō* three times.

Secular Shu Special Prayer

Services in the Nichiren Shu tradition range from simple to ornate and are performed in temples or at home altars, usually featuring a calligraphic mandala or a statue of the Buddha. In this tradition, Sakyamuni is honored as the eternal Buddha and Nichiren Shonin as a bodhisattva. Depending on which branch of Nichiren Shu one belongs to, ceremonies may include one or more of the following: reciting the opening prose section of the second chapter of the Lotus Sūtra, the verse section of the sixteenth chapter, the Expedients section of Chapter Two, the Triple World Parable in Chapter Three, and sections of Chapters Ten and Eleven, along with chanting Namu Myōhō Renge Kyō. Following these recitations, a special prayer is often read aloud.³ The following secular prayer is intended to replace the traditional version:

With faith's highest virtue sourced in immanence, the ability to shape our lives in its likeness depends on sincere and thoughtful effort alone. This ceremony supports the effort.

Our sacred image has come to represent the conditional emergence of benevolence as gifted by time, process, and potential. Though relieved of its supernatural foundations, it continues to project an inherent pureness that can surpass and better both civil and religious authority, and encourage the pursuit of a more peaceful world.

The prayer hereby replaced recognized the eternal Buddha Sakyamuni, protective deities, and Nichiren Shonin's predicted appearance in the prophetic age of the Latter Day of the Law. It also paid homage to the spirits of the universe. For some, the transcendent elements of the prior prayer still resonate. For others, they are remnants of the past, especially now when there is a path forward without them.

To introduce a grounded principle for divine inspiration, the *Lotus Sūtra's* revelation of an ever-present Buddha was interpreted to be a universal ethic established by the temporal realm. The implications are liberating, for the ultimate insight is no longer limited to a mystical union subject to sectarian custody, but observed firsthand in the natural order and open for emulation based on one's best judgment.

This practice merges the meaning of this prayer with the rhythm of a twice-daily recitation from the *Lotus Sūtra*. And, while chanting *Namu Myoho Renge Kyō*, it welcomes reflection on such matters as overcoming difficulties, personal growth, and the advancement of a common good. Our purpose is to carry on with a tradition long dedicated to cultivating a blend of wisdom and compassion in all.

³ Based on a review of *The Liturgy of Nichiren Shu*, 2015, The Nichiren Shu International Center, Hayward, CA. See pp. 37-38. The following links are to a copy of the Nichiren Shu liturgy and a picture of their image of reverence: <https://web.archive.org/web/20250424115742/https://www.500yojanas.org/the-basic-nichiren-shu-service/#prayer> and <https://web.archive.org/web/20230607031613/https://www.lionsroar.com/what-is-the-gohonzon/>.

Secular Independent Prayer

Spiral Flower Graphic by Robert Dixon, 1987. *Mathographics*, (p. 137). Dover Publications, NY.
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The above graphic is a suggested object of veneration for an independent secular practice. Instead of the traditional invocation, practitioners can chant “Nam Rihō no Chihi Sō” (Reverence for the emergence of wisdom and compassion from the natural order).

While traditional recitations from the Lotus Sūtra’s second and sixteenth chapters remain an option, a formal ritual may not always be necessary. At one’s discretion, occasionally recalling ‘The conditional emergence of benevolence as gifted by time, process, and potential’ or just ‘the benevolent aspects of existence’ may be sufficient.

If a formal ritual is performed, consider the following prayer:

With faith’s highest virtue sourced in immanence, the ability to shape our lives in its likeness depends on sincere and thoughtful effort alone. This ceremony supports the effort.

Our sacred image represents the conditional emergence of benevolence as gifted by time, process, and potential. Thus endowed, it projects an inherent pureness free of transcendence that can surpass and better both civil and religious authority, while encouraging the pursuit of a more peaceful world.

When existence itself assumes the role of divine inspiration, the deities of the past fade into a universal ethic established by the temporal realm. The implications are liberating, for the ultimate truth is no longer a mystical reality subject to sectarian custody, but observed firsthand in the natural order and open for emulation based on one’s best judgment.

Our practice merges the meaning of this prayer with the rhythm of chanting *Nam Rihō no Chihi Sō* and welcomes reflection on such matters as overcoming difficulties, personal growth, and the advancement of a common good. We strive to cultivate a blend of wisdom and compassion in all.